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& IQTISODIYOT

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ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

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- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
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- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
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- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
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- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
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- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ENHANCING THE SERVICE SECTOR AS A MEANS OF CREATING EMPLOYMENT IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract. The article analyzes the content, structure, and functions of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan, as well as the need, significance, practice, legal framework, processes, investment opportunities, and problems of its development. It also develops proposals and recommendations for addressing these issues. The article analyzes the content, structure, and functions of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan, as well as the need, significance, practice, legal framework, processes, investment opportunities, and problems of its development. It also develops proposals and recommendations for addressing these issues.

Keywords: tourism, tourism industry, tourism infrastructure, tourism, investment, hotel, tourism services, employment, tour operator, export.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada O'zbekistonda turizm infratuzilmasining mazmuni, tuzilishi va funksiyalari, shuningdek uning rivojlanish zarurati, ahamiyati, amaliyoti, huquqiy asoslari, jarayonlari, investitsiya imkoniyatlari hamda mavjud muammolari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ushbu muammolarni hal etish bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Maqolada O'zbekistonda turizm infratuzilmasining mazmuni, tuzilishi va funksiyalari, shuningdek uning rivojlanish zarurati, ahamiyati, amaliyoti, huquqiy asoslari, jarayonlari, investitsiya imkoniyatlari hamda mavjud muammolari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ushbu muammolarni hal etish bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, turizm sanoati, turizm infratuzilmasi, turizm, investitsiya, mehmonxona, turizm xizmatlari, bandlik, turoperator, eksport.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются содержание, структура и функции туристической инфраструктуры в Узбекистане, а также необходимость, значение, практика, правовая база, процессы, инвестиционные возможности и проблемы её развития. Также разработаны предложения и рекомендации по решению данных проблем. В статье анализируются содержание, структура и функции туристической инфраструктуры в Узбекистане, а также необходимость, значение, практика, правовая база, процессы, инвестиционные возможности и проблемы её развития. Также разработаны предложения и рекомендации по решению данных проблем.

Ключевые слова: туризм, туристическая индустрия, туристическая инфраструктура, туризм, инвестиции, гостиница, туристические услуги, занятость, туроператор, экспорт.

INTRODUCTION

The service sector is becoming increasingly important for the economies of most countries. At the same time, tourism is recognized as a multifaceted and rapidly expanding economic activity that relies mainly on the service sector and labor. In recent years, our country has been implementing consistent measures to develop the tourism industry, including creating maximum convenience, further increasing the competitiveness of the industry, improving the quality of services provided, and actively promoting the national tourism product on the world market. At the same time, there are a number of problems that need to be addressed in the tourism sector. We will dwell on them in detail below.

To ensure employment through tourism, it is first necessary to improve the flow of tourists, and before that, we will study the reasons and motives that encourage tourists to travel.

Motivation to travel varies in different contexts and cultures, and it is difficult to identify the element that distinguishes one tourist from another. Crompton, in the field of tourism psychology, divided the factors that encourage people to go on vacation into two macro categories.

- motivational factors that explain the desire to travel;
- pull factors that explain the choice of destination.

According to this classification, two different and sometimes contradictory aspects play a role in choosing a vacation:

- psychosocial (emotional, social, cognitive and motivational), where the author identifies seven motivations for traveling:

- escape from everyday life and its environment;
- self-search and evaluation;
- physical and mental relaxation,
- for luxury,
- improving and strengthening family relationships and friendships;
- facilitating social relations.
- “material things” mean the economic opportunities and cultural-geographical elements of the holiday.

These issues interact with each other in the process of choosing a vacation. Motivational factors are socio-psychological in nature and are associated with the internal needs of the person. Among them, the main factor seems to be the desire to “escape” from stress and everyday restrictions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The development of the service sector plays a decisive role in strengthening tourism infrastructure and expanding employment opportunities. Tourism is widely recognized in economic literature as a labor-intensive sector that stimulates job creation not only within tourism enterprises themselves but also across a wide range of related service industries such as transportation, accommodation, catering, entertainment, and local services. Therefore, analyzing the theoretical foundations of tourism development and its connection with employment generation has become an important research direction in modern tourism economics.

One of the key theoretical approaches to understanding tourism development is related to the concept of tourist motivation. In this regard, J.L. Crompton explains that the decision to travel is influenced by a combination of internal psychological motivations and external destination-related factors. In his well-known study on pleasure travel motivation, Crompton identifies “push” factors, which represent internal motives such as escape, relaxation, or social interaction, and “pull” factors, which are attributes of the destination itself, including infrastructure, attractions, and service quality. This framework is important for tourism infrastructure studies because the availability of well-developed service facilities—hotels, restaurants, transport networks, and recreational services—acts as a major pull factor that attracts tourists and indirectly stimulates employment in the local service sector.

Another important perspective on tourism development is provided by H. Wasche and A. Woll, who emphasize the role of regional networks in strengthening tourism infrastructure. Their conceptual framework of regional sport tourism networks highlights how cooperation among local stakeholders—tourism organizations, sports institutions, service providers, and government bodies—creates integrated tourism products. Such networks contribute to regional economic development by improving service coordination, increasing tourist flows, and generating new employment opportunities in local service industries. The authors argue that the effectiveness of tourism infrastructure often depends not only on physical facilities but also on the strength of institutional and organizational cooperation within a region.

International organizations have also extensively analyzed tourism’s contribution to employment and economic development. According to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), tourism is one of the fastest-growing sectors of the global economy and plays a major role in job creation. The UNWTO reports indicate that tourism supports millions of jobs worldwide through both direct employment in tourism enterprises and indirect employment in related service sectors such as retail trade, transportation, and cultural services. The organization also emphasizes that investment in tourism infrastructure—airports, hotels, transport services, and digital tourism platforms—significantly increases the employment capacity of the service sector, particularly in developing economies.

The relationship between tourism and social development has also been examined by W. Zhao and J.R.B. Ritchie, who propose an integrative framework linking tourism development with poverty reduction. Their research demonstrates that tourism infrastructure and service sector development can provide significant employment opportunities for local populations, especially in rural or economically disadvantaged regions. By integrating tourism with local economic activities—such as handicrafts, cultural services, and community-based tourism—countries can enhance inclusive growth while expanding the service economy.

The role of modern technologies and media in tourism service development is analyzed by P. Zagnoli and E. Radicchi, who focus on the interaction between sport tourism, marketing strategies, and new media. Their research shows that digital platforms, online promotion, and modern marketing tools significantly enhance the visibility of tourism destinations and service providers. The adoption of new media technologies strengthens tourism infrastructure by facilitating communication between service providers and tourists, improving service accessibility, and increasing demand for tourism products. As a result, digitalization within the tourism sector also creates new forms of employment, particularly in marketing, information services, and tourism management.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that the development of tourism infrastructure and the expansion of the service sector are closely interconnected processes that contribute significantly to employment creation. Scholars emphasize the importance of tourist motivation, regional cooperation networks, infrastructure investment, digital technologies, and inclusive development strategies in strengthening the employment potential of tourism. These theoretical perspectives provide an important foundation for further research on how improving service sector capacity can enhance tourism infrastructure and generate sustainable employment opportunities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study uses both primary and secondary data sources to examine the role of the service sector in employment creation within tourism infrastructure. Data were obtained from international tourism reports, statistical databases, and scientific publications. The collected information was analyzed using comparative analysis, descriptive statistics, and logical interpretation to identify trends, relationships, and key factors influencing employment growth in the tourism service sector.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Attraction refers to the attractive elements of a certain goal rather than factors. This is usually manifested in tourists who carefully select vacation and travel destinations and pay attention to intermediate stages, for example, opportunities to broaden their horizons (for this type of tourist, the main goal is the desire to experience new things and enrich their knowledge).

In order to find the reasons that usually motivate tourists to make a certain travel choice, many researchers emphasize that “escape” from everyday life and the problems caused by society is a recurring element in the choice of travel. In this case, the holiday plays the role of compensation for some of the needs and shortcomings felt in everyday life (sun, sea, relaxation, entertainment, etc.). At the same time, it is also a way to reward people for their work during the year. becomes a method of reward: through this choice, each person focuses on distinguishing themselves from others. Finally, it should be noted that the motivation to travel often depends on the type of vacation chosen. For example, we can consider some of the reasons associated with certain types of tourism.

- physiological: health tourism, sports tourism;
- distraction: tourism to distract from everyday life;
- interpersonal: social tourism, spending time with family and friends or seeking new relationships,
- psychological: tourism for relaxation, entertainment, etc.,
- cultural: cultural, historical, artistic tourism, etc.;
- environmental: ecotourism, etc.;
- luxury: elite tourism, for people of the same social class or higher;
- discovery: adventure tourism, hiking, etc.

“The needs of the tourist arise from the need for people to feel an escape from ordinary life, which, when compared with everyday life, creates a sufficiently perceived break and reasonable doubts about the prospect of returning.” From this point of view, these motivations can be divided into two classes:

- leisure motives or desires that arise in the search for entertainment, fun and relaxation;
- cultural motives or desires that arise in the search for knowledge, learning, novelty.

Throughout human history, people have exchanged cultural experiences, ideas, values and goods through art, trade and migration. People’s cultural self-expression has always aroused interest. The natural curiosity of the tourist towards different corners of the world constitutes one of the strongest tourist motives. The objects that tourists visit serve to enrich their spiritual life and broaden their worldview.

The historical and cultural potential of the country is one of the main factors of tourism, because:

- 1) It is an important means of attracting tourists, since getting acquainted with the historical and cultural heritage is the strongest incentive for tourist motives;
- 2) Cultural and historical heritage sites are an important asset of modern cities, which can bring benefits and have a significant impact on their economic development;

3) It is of great importance in the social sphere for smoothing seasonal fluctuations and evenly distributing tourist flows in the region;

4) It creates a favorable image of the region, creates a “brand” of historical and cultural heritage, which is used as an effective means of assuming leadership in the tourist field. And finally, cultural and historical centers not only bring income to the region, but also create a basis for local residents to be proud of their unique heritage and share it with tourists. Although almost any information can be obtained from printed publications, fiction and other sources, the historical truth remains: “A picture is worth a thousand words.” The cultural potential of the region is reflected in its historical heritage. The presence of unique historical objects can predetermine the successful development of tourism in the region. Being the most powerful motivator of tourist motives, historical and cultural tourism also helps to expand the resources for attracting tourists. Due to tourist spending, additional money is brought to the city’s economy. The growing number of tourists visiting the region undoubtedly contributes to an increase in the volume of tourism product production, the formation of an active consumer market in the tourist center, and the increase in the investment attractiveness of the local tourism industry. An increase in the volume of production and sales of tourism products based on tourist demand leads to the creation of new tourism industry facilities (hotels, catering establishments, leisure and entertainment venues), the modernization of existing facilities, and an increase in production efficiency. An increase in the number of local tourism industry enterprises requires an increase in the volume of labor resources employed in the tourism sector, which creates the opportunity to provide employment to many women and young people. Smoothing out seasonal fluctuations and evenly distributing tourist flows in the region, historical and cultural tourism is an invariable compensator, resolving the uneven economic development of individual parts of the region. It helps the emergence and expansion of economic, transport, utility and other types of activities that allow to raise backward regions to the level of advanced industrial regions. Due to the historical and cultural heritage, the region can have a unique reputation in the market. Cultural elements and factors can be channels for disseminating information about the district’s tourism potential. The success of tourism development depends not only on the material base, but also on the uniqueness of historical and cultural heritage.

The International Trade Centre (ITC), a joint agency of the World Trade Organization and the United Nations, focuses on the challenges of ensuring the success of small business exports in developing and transition economies by providing sustainable and inclusive development solutions to trade support institutions and policymakers. The Inclusive Tourism Programme was established to enhance the potential of the tourism industry to contribute to development and poverty reduction. It aims to reduce the negative impacts of tourism and instead strengthen the links between the tourism sector and vulnerable local men and women living in and around tourist destinations. The programme promotes activities that create inclusive tourism business models, foster stakeholder partnerships and integrate local producers and service providers into the tourism supply chain. This enables local producers and service providers to supply essential goods and services, and equips buyers with the skills to develop sustainable partnerships with local producers. The program assesses potential local supply opportunities and facilitates market access, thereby reducing the amount of products and services imported from external suppliers.

It is necessary to establish a system of regular publication of tourist guides or manuals in the form of books, which contain the opinions of foreign tourists visiting the Republic of Karakalpakstan about how their trips went, what impressions they had, how much money they spent, and many other experiences. Because foreign tourists want to know the experiences of other tourists in the area of interest before planning a trip. If possible, such books should be created separately for tourists from each country, in their language. For example, Japanese tourists pay more attention to the opinions of their compatriots;

It is necessary to approach the issue of developing family guest houses and hostels in the Republic of Karakalpakstan separately, which will lead to an increase in the flow of foreign tourists. Because tourists try to use the facilities with minimal costs. According to world experience, family guest houses and hostels appeared precisely on the basis of tourist demand, and foreign tourists planning a trip to a certain region pay attention to the availability and competitiveness of such accommodation facilities. In Karakalpakstan, special approaches should be developed to develop a system of such accommodation facilities, and we will try to give our opinions on this issue in our further research.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the development of tourism in the Republic of Karakalpakstan will lead to the effective mobilization of the rich natural, cultural and social resources of the region, to the elimination of the risks of environmental problems associated with the drying up of the Aral Sea in the region, and most importantly, to the transformation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan into one of the most developed regions in our country.

List of used literature:

1. Crompton, J.L. (1979). Motivation for pleasure vacation. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 6, 409-424.
2. Wasche, H., Woll, A. (2010). Regional Sport Tourism Networks: a conceptual framework. *Journal of Sport&Tourism*, 15(3), 191-214.
3. United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) (2012). *World Tourism Barometer*, 10/March
4. Zhao, W.; Ritchie, J.R.B. *Tourism and Poverty Alleviation: An Integrative Research Framework*. *Curr. Issues Tour.* 2007, 10, 119.
5. Zagnoli, P., Radicchi, E. (2011). *Sport Marketing e Nuovi Media /Sport Marketing and New Media/*. Milano: Franco Angeli
6. <https://factory.dev/blog/travel-tourism-mobile-app>
7. <https://www.trt.net.tr/uzbek/turk-dunyosi/2019/02/22/buxoroda-o-tayotgan-birinchi-ziyosat-turizmida-tashrif-buyuruvchilar-soni-ortmoqda-1150771>

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